

Versio 18.8.2021

CRUISE REPORT

R/V Aranda

Cruise 02/2022

CABLE leg 1
4.4.2022 – 9.4.2022

This report is based on preliminary data and is subject to changes.

Chief Scientist: Taavi Liblik

Objectives of the cruise

The main objectives of the cruise were:

- deploy current-meter moorings to the central Baltic Sea;
- deploy wave buoys and current meter mooring to the Gulf of Finland;
- replace wave buoy near Gotland Island;
- recover Argo float in the Eastern Gotland Basin;
- Conduct vertical profiling and sampling for nutrient analyses in the zonal transect in the Baltic Proper and at the transect from the southern Baltic to the Gulf of Finland.
- Collect surface sediment samples and sediment cores from selected stations.

There were 14 persons working onboard to achieve the objectives (see table 7).

Daily logbook**04.08.2022**

We departed from Helsinki 8 AM local time (5 AM UTC). Air temperature varied in the range of + 1 to +3 °C. Wind mostly with the speed of 10-15 m/s from south and southeast prevailed during the day. See Fig. 2 for meteorological conditions onboard.

First, two wave buoy moorings (AALTO_STAD and AALTO_HKI) were deployed by FMI. ADCP current profiler was deployed to the AALTO_HKI as well. We also conducted CTD profiling for testing and training purposes in both locations. The first CTD station had index 57.

After the deployments, we headed east to the Estonian national monitoring station F1, from where we started a section along the thalweg of the Gulf of Finland towards the west. From selected stations, nutrient samples and surface sediments were collected.

One person felt sick (fever) in the evening and he isolated himself in the cabin. He made a covid test, which was negative.

Table 1. Stations made on 4th April

CTD index	Hour UTC	Minute UTC	CTD station count	Station name	Moorings/float
57	6	36	1	AALTO_STAD	Wave buoy deployment (FMI)
58	9	40	2	AALTO_HKI	Wave buoy and ADCP deployment (FMI)
59	15	0	3	F1	
60	17	15	4	AG14	
61	19	10	5	AG13	
62	20	42	6	AG12	
63	22	30	7	AG11	

05.08.2022

We continued towards west and conducted measurements at the thalweg of the section.

Air temperature varied in the range of 0 to +1 °C and wind from south and southeast, mostly with speed of 10-15 m/s prevailed until 08:00 UTC. After that the wind turned to west and its speed increased over 20 m/s. We stopped working, when the vessel was not able to keep its position at station AG4. Wind speed stayed over 20 m/s for eight hours and was around 25 m/s for few hours. We continued heading towards west, but with speed of 2-3 knots. Weather improved at night and we headed towards M10 station (near Vilsandi Island).

Measurements in the Gulf of Finland revealed weak haline and inversed thermal stratification and elevated Chl-a values in the upper layer. Deep layer was isolated by well defined halocline. There was longitudinal salinity gradient, both in the upper layer and in the deep layer. Likewise, temperature and oxygen gradient observed in the deep layer along the gulf. Dissolved oxygen was around 3 mg/l in the easternmost part of the section, but zero in the easternmost part of the section. Note that the main CTD-Rosette oxygen sensor had slight oxygen offset, around 0.07 ml/l.

Table 2. Stations made on 5th April

CTD index	Hour UTC	Minute UTC	CTD station count	Station name
64	0	5	8	AG10
65	1	22	9	Keri
66	3	5	10	AG9
67	4	30	11	AG8
68	5	45	12	AG7
69	7	13	13	AG6
70	9	0	14	AG5

06.08.2022

Today we spent our day in deploying moorings across the Baltic Proper. It was quite challenging in the morning as waves were still quite high, but it calmed down in the afternoon. It went more or less smoothly, except at M8, where we deployed the mooring first too early- failure with releasing of the mooring. We collected the mooring again and deployed it again. In all stations, CTD profiles and water samples for nutrient analysis were collected.

After mooring deployments, we decided to leave the section and head to south, in order to reach the Argo float in daylight next day.

Table 3. Stations made on 6th April

CTD index	Hour UTC	Minute UTC	CTD station count	Station name	Moorings/floats
71	5	6	15	M10	Single point current meter (TalTech)
72	8	22	16	M9	ADCP+CTD (LIAE)
73	11	30	17	M8	ADCP (TalTech)
74	17	0	18	M7	ADCP (SMHI)
75	20	0	19	M6	ADCP (FMI)
76	22	35	20	M5	ADCP (FMI)

07.08.2022

We started work near Gotland Island, recovered wavebuoy and deployed new one. Secondly, we picked up Argo float southwest from the Gotland Deep. CTD-profile at the pickup location was conducted to calibrate the Argo float sensors. In the afternoon, we started the section from Gotland Deep (BY15) towards Gulf of Finland. There was moderate wind 6-12 m/s from southwest during the day.

Water column was well mixed down to the halocline in the Baltic Proper. Although Chl-a fluorescence still showed slightly elevated values in the upper layer. Anoxia was established below the sharp halocline. Small intrusion of warmer and saltier water was found in the depth of 110 in the Gotland Deep. The intrusion contained small amount of oxygen, unlike the water below and above the feature.

Table 4. Stations made on 7th April

CTD index	Hour UTC	Minute UTC	CTD station count	Station name	Moorings/floats
				Gotland Wave buoy	Wave buoy (FMI)
77	11	48	21	Argo22	Argo float (FMI)
78	14	0	22	BY15	
79	16	55	23	GD1	
80	19	0	24	GD0	
81	20	35	25	FD1	
82	23	8	26	TF286	

08.08.2022

We continued the cruise with CTD stations in the Farö Deep and completed the zonal section (M2-M4). We used another CTD to record the last meters above seafloor at M3. After M2 we continued towards the Gulf of Finland. Strong SW wind and high waves made us stop sampling after station NBP10. Thus, we headed towards the Gulf of Finland and hoped to continue sampling if the weather improves.

We noted that there is an offset in the pressure sensor of the main CTD: -1.4 db. It used to be -0.7 db in March 2022 according to FMI.

Table 5. Stations made on 8th April.

CTD index	Hour UTC	Minute UTC	CTD station count	Station name
83	2	7	27	NBP2
84	3	56	28	M4
85	5	15	29	M3
86	6	52	30	M2
87	8	15	31	NBP4
88	10	0	32	NBP5
89	11	30	33	NBP6
90	13	20	34	NBP8

09.08.2022

We continued sampling at station NBP14. We made a repeat CTD profile (the first profile was made on the 5th of April) at AG5. A comparison of profiles revealed the vertical mixing and weakening of the stratification had occurred in the upper part of the water column. The deep layer was fresher compared to the previous measurement, indicating the reversal of estuarine circulation due to southwesterly wind impulse. After AG5 we headed to Helsinki and arrived there around 17:00 UTC.

Table 7. The scientific crew.

Name	On board	Organization
Taavi Liblik	04-09.04.2022	TalTech
Sirje Sildever	04-09.04.2022	TalTech
Kristian Pärt	04-09.04.2022	TalTech
Fred Buschmann	04-09.04.2022	TalTech
Villu Kikas	04-09.04.2022	TalTech
Oliver Samlas	04-09.04.2022	TalTech
Kai Salm	04-09.04.2022	TalTech
Diana Maslova	04-09.04.2022	TalTech
Maris Skudra	04-09.04.2022	LIAE
Miks Papirtis	04-09.04.2022	LIAE
Erkka Itonen	04-09.04.2022	FMI
Sami Pusa	04-09.04.2022	FMI
Simo-Matti Siiriä	04-09.04.2022	FMI
Tuomo Roine	04-09.04.2022	FMI

Figure 1. Cruise route.

Figure 2. Meteorological conditions during the cruise.

Conclusions

Overall, the cruise was successful, the primary goals were achieved.

We experienced unusually strong wind event for the spring season. We observed weak haline and inversed thermal stratification and elevated Chl-a values in the upper layer in the Gulf of Finland. The water column was well mixed down to the halocline in the Baltic Proper. Anoxia was established below the sharp halocline in the Baltic Proper while ca 3 mg/l oxygen concentration was observed in the central Gulf of Finland. There was a longitudinal gradient of oxygen, salinity, and temperature between the central Gulf of Finland and northern Baltic Proper. Likewise, a gradient existed in the upper layer: water in the gulf was colder and fresher.

I would like to thank the scientific team and the ship crew for their good collaboration in the challenging and very variable weather conditions.

Index 0057, AALTO_STAD 60° 7.360' N, 24° 58.370' E, time 2022-04-04, 06.41, depth 21.0 m
Index 0058, AALTO_HKI 59° 57.940' N, 25° 13.990' E, time 2022-04-04, 09.45, depth 63.0 m
Index 0059, F1 59° 54.960' N, 26° 20.570' E, time 2022-04-04, 15.38, depth 83.0 m
Index 0060, AG14 59° 52.200' N, 26° 6.240' E, time 2022-04-04, 17.18, depth 75.0 m
Index 0061, AG13 59° 49.460' N, 25° 51.920' E, time 2022-04-04, 19.12, depth 97.0 m
Index 0062, AG12 59° 46.730' N, 25° 37.670' E, time 2022-04-04, 20.45, depth 99.0 m
Index 0063, AG11 59° 45.100' N, 25° 27.120' E, time 2022-04-04, 22.38, depth 87.0 m
Index 0064, AG10 59° 39.610' N, 25° 14.390' E, time 2022-04-05, 00.06, depth 112.0 m
Index 0065, KERI 59° 42.970' N, 25° 0.870' E, time 2022-04-05, 01.23, depth 102.0 m
Index 0066, AG9 59° 42.500' N, 24° 49.790' E, time 2022-04-05, 03.05, depth 85.0 m
Index 0067, AG8 59° 43.070' N, 24° 32.150' E, time 2022-04-05, 04.34, depth 93.0 m
Index 0068, AG7 59° 39.980' N, 24° 20.770' E, time 2022-04-05, 05.45, depth 90.0 m
Index 0069, AG6 59° 33.570' N, 24° 7.190' E, time 2022-04-05, 07.19, depth 86.0 m
Index 0070, AG5 59° 29.590' N, 23° 54.050' E, time 2022-04-05, 09.05, depth 89.0 m
Index 0071, M10 58° 24.750' N, 21° 44.370' E, time 2022-04-06, 05.07, depth 38.0 m
Index 0072, M9 58° 24.750' N, 21° 28.380' E, time 2022-04-06, 08.26, depth 69.0 m
Index 0073, M8 58° 24.740' N, 21° 12.390' E, time 2022-04-06, 11.30, depth 92.0 m
Index 0074, M7 58° 24.740' N, 20° 59.990' E, time 2022-04-06, 17.00, depth 94.0 m
Index 0075, M6 58° 24.730' N, 20° 40.470' E, time 2022-04-06, 20.06, depth 101.0 m
Index 0076, M5 58° 24.740' N, 20° 24.500' E, time 2022-04-06, 22.38, depth 131.0 m
Index 0077, ARGO22 57° 11.050' N, 19° 36.740' E, time 2022-04-07, 11.47, depth 143.0 m
Index 0078, BY15 57° 18.990' N, 20° 7.500' E, time 2022-04-07, 14.08, depth 240.0 m
Index 0079, GD1 57° 34.330' N, 20° 9.020' E, time 2022-04-07, 16.57, depth 154.0 m
Index 0080, GD0 57° 42.010' N, 20° 10.010' E, time 2022-04-07, 18.50, depth 127.0 m
Index 0081, FD1 57° 51.020' N, 20° 3.040' E, time 2022-04-07, 20.38, depth 145.0 m
Index 0082, TF286 58° 0.010' N, 19° 53.960' E, time 2022-04-07, 23.08, depth 191.0 m
Index 0083, NBP2 58° 16.410' N, 19° 54.600' E, time 2022-04-08, 02.07, depth 149.0 m
Index 0084, M4 58° 24.750' N, 20° 3.010' E, time 2022-04-08, 03.58, depth 115.0 m
Index 0085, M3 58° 24.760' N, 19° 52.490' E, time 2022-04-08, 05.16, depth 118.0 m
Index 0086, M2 58° 24.760' N, 19° 44.590' E, time 2022-04-08, 06.56, depth 93.0 m
Index 0087, NBP4 58° 30.000' N, 19° 50.040' E, time 2022-04-08, 08.19, depth 158.0 m
Index 0088, NBP5 58° 37.220' N, 19° 54.020' E, time 2022-04-08, 10.04, depth 177.0 m
Index 0089, NBP6 58° 42.600' N, 19° 58.200' E, time 2022-04-08, 11.40, depth 192.0 m
Index 0090, NBP8 58° 50.980' N, 20° 12.090' E, time 2022-04-08, 13.20, depth 201.0 m
Index 0091, NBP10 58° 56.390' N, 20° 43.810' E, time 2022-04-08, 19.29, depth 217.0 m
Index 0092, NBP14 59° 13.680' N, 22° 10.360' E, time 2022-04-09, 01.15, depth 139.0 m
Index 0093, NBP15 59° 19.530' N, 22° 23.980' E, time 2022-04-09, 03.05, depth 145.0 m
Index 0094, NBP16 59° 17.980' N, 22° 47.440' E, time 2022-04-09, 05.03, depth 140.0 m
Index 0095, NBP17 59° 20.020' N, 23° 1.310' E, time 2022-04-09, 06.29, depth 124.0 m
Index 0096, AG3 59° 25.040' N, 23° 27.480' E, time 2022-04-09, 08.39, depth 109.0 m
Index 0097, AG5 59° 29.610' N, 23° 54.060' E, time 2022-04-09, 10.52, depth 94.0 m